

MOTHERS' KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES AND EDUCATION RELATED TO TODDLERS' VISITS TO INTEGRATED SERVICE POST (POSYANDU)

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Abstract

Background: The lack of visits by toddlers to the Integrated Service Post (Posyandu) results in children's unmonitored growth and development so that growth faltering can be detected early. The reality in the field shows that visits by toddlers to posyandu are still lacking. Data from the Dolo Health Center is that it was found that the target of toddlers in Kotarindau Village in 2023 is 346 toddlers, of which only 185 toddlers (53.46%) came to be weighed so the level of compliance in posyandu visits has not reached the target. The purpose of this study is to know the factors related to toddlers' visits to the posyandu in Kotarindau Village, Dolo District, and Sigi Regency. **Methods:** This study is a type of Cross-Sectional research, with a sample of 64 mothers who have toddlers in Kotarindau Village, independent variables of knowledge, attitude, and education, dependent variables of visits to posyandu toddlers, questionnaire research instruments, univariate and bivariate data analysis with the Chi-Square test. **Results:** there was a relationship between maternal knowledge and toddlers' visits to the posyandu with a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$, there was a relationship between maternal attitudes and toddlers' visits to the posyandu with a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$, and there was a relationship between maternal education and toddlers' visits to the posyandu with a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. **Conclusion:** there is a relationship between knowledge, attitude and education factors with toddler visits to posyandu in Kotarindau village, Dolo District, Sigi Regency. Suggestion For health workers in the Kotarindau Village work area, it is necessary to collaborate with cadres to provide counseling to mothers with toddlers in increasing the knowledge of mothers under five about the importance of visiting toddlers to posyandu to prevent stunting in toddlers from an early age.

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Education, Visits, Posyandu, Toddlers

1. INTRODUCTION

Monitoring the growth of toddlers is very important to find out growth barriers (*growth faltering*) early. Growth and development in toddlers can be monitored through monthly weighing of the child. Weighing toddlers can be done in various places such as the Integrated Service Post (posyandu) ¹. Posyandu is assumed to be one of the right approaches to reduce the mortality and illness rate of toddlers and can improve the nutritional status of toddlers ². The frequency of visits by toddlers can measure the coverage of weighing toddlers to weigh themselves regularly for the last six months ¹.

According to World Health Organization (WHO) data in 2022, there are 148.1 million children under the age of 5 who are too short for their age (stunting), 45 million children who are too thin for their height (*wasting*), and 37.0 million children who are overweight for their height (*overweight*)³. Based on data reporting in Indonesia published in 2021 by Public Health Data Communication, the achievement of the percentage of children under five whose growth and development are monitored is 68.90% of the target of 70%⁴. One of the reasons for the failure to achieve the coverage target for the percentage of children under five whose growth and development are monitored is due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which arises due to the suspension of services in several Posyandu (46% of Puskesmas have no Posyandu activities and 35% of Puskesmas reported a decrease in services)⁴. In Central Sulawesi Province in 2024, the target is 241,365 children, and only 166,930 (69.2%) children under five are measured in weight and height. Meanwhile, at the Dolo Health Center in Kotarindu Village in 2023, there are 346 children under five (53.46%), while only 185 children under five (53.46%) are actively visiting the posyandu.

Visits to posyandu for toddlers that are still lacking can cause several adverse impacts, including unmonitored child growth and development and delayed early detection of nutritional problems⁵. Toddlers who are defined as children in the age range of 0-59 months are stated to have their growth and development monitored well if in one year they are weighed at least 8 times, their body length or height is measured at least 2 times in a year and their development is also monitored at least 2 times in a year⁴.

Mothers' knowledge about Posyandu makes them always bring their children to Posyandu so that it is easy to monitor their growth and development, while for mothers who lack knowledge, the number of visits is also less, This is due to the lack of knowledge of mothers about activities in Posyandu⁶. Mothers who are not present at the posyandu are worried that information or knowledge about health does not reach all goals, so the goal of changing daily attitudes to behave healthily is difficult to achieve. In fact, posyandu is a place to provide educational information, in addition to other driving factors that affect mothers' visits. Therefore, it is necessary to review the factors of knowledge, attitude, and education that affect visits at the Posyandu Toddler⁷.

Education also affects the visit of mothers at posyandu, higher education will make it easier to understand information, if higher education, then maintaining health is very concern, including how to take care of babies and toddlers and regulate balanced nutrition. On the other hand, with low education, it is very difficult to translate the information obtained, both from health workers and from other media^{8,9}. This background shows that further analysis is needed on factors related to toddler visits to posyandu. The purpose of this study is to find out the factors related to toddler visits to posyandu in Kotarindu Village, Dolo District, Sigi Regency.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study is an analytical correlation research with a cross-sectional approach conducted in Kotarindu Village, Dolo District, Sigi Regency. The sample in this study is 185 mothers who have toddlers. The sample amounted to 64 people who were taken by proportional random sampling. The independent variables are in the form of knowledge, attitude, and education while the dependent variables are in the form of visits to the posyandu toddlers. Knowledge is divided into 3 measurement results with criteria of good (correct answer 76%-100%), fair (correct answer 57%-75%), and poor (correct answer <56%). The results of the attitude measurement were in the form of caring (answer score $\geq 50\%$) and not caring

(answer score <50%). Education has 3 measurement results, namely elementary education (SD-SMP), secondary education (SMA), and higher education (D3/S1-S2). The results of the Posyandu visit measurement are good if the visit is >8 times per year and less if the visit is ≤ 8 times per year.

Data was collected using questionnaires consisting of knowledge questionnaires in the form of multiple choice questions with 10 questions, and attitude questionnaires in the form of Likert scales with 10 statements. The validity test results were 0.77 and the reliability showed 0.69. This study uses univariate analysis, then a bivariate test is carried out using the chi-square test. This research has gone through an ethical study at the Palu Ministry of Health Polytechnic No:001287/KEPK POLTEKKES KEMENKESPALU/2024.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Characteristics Responden

Table 1: Frequency distribution of respondent characteristics.

Characteristic	Distribution	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
19-24 Years	23	35,9
25-35 Years	32	50,0
>35 years old	9	14,1
Education		
Elementary	17	26,6
Secondary	45	70,3
Higher	2	3,1
Work		
Not Working	64	100
Work	0	0
Sum	64	100

Based on table 1, it shows that the most maternal age, which is 25-35 years old, amounted to 32 people 50%, while the education of most secondary mothers was 45 people (70.3%) and all mothers did not work (100%).

3.2 Frequency Distribution of Factors Related to Posyandu Toddler Visits

Table 2: Frequency distribution of factors related to toddler visits.

Factors	Distribution	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Knowledge		
Good	32	50,0
Enough	20	31,3
Less	12	18,8
Attitude		
Care	31	48,4
No Matter	33	51,6
Visit		
Good	36	56,3
Less	28	43,8
Sum	64	100

Based on table 2, the most dominant respondents' knowledge was the good category of 32 people (50%), the attitude was dominated by indifference as many as 33 people (51.6%) and the most good visits were 36 people (56.3%).

3.3 Bivariate Analysis of Factors Related to Toddler Visits to Posyandu

Table 3: Relationship between maternal knowledge, attitudes and education with visits by toddlers to posyandu

Factors	Visit				P-Value
	Good		Less		
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	
Knowledge					
Good	31	48,43	1	1,56	0,000
Enough	4	6,25	16	25,0	
Less	1	1,56	11	17,19	
Attitude					
Care	28	43,75	3	4,69	0,000
No Matter	8	12,50	25	39,06	
Education					
Elementary	5	7,81	12	18,75	0,006
Secondary	29	45,31	16	25,0	
Higher	2	3,13	0	0	

Based on table 3, it is known that the value of $p\text{-value} < 0.005$ so that there is a relationship between knowledge, attitude and education and visits by toddlers to posyandu in Kotarindu Village, Dolo District, Sigi Regency

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 The Relationship between Mother's Knowledge and Toddler's Visit to the Posyandu

Knowledge was mostly good and good visits amounted to 31 people (48.43%) while those who visited less amounted to 1 person (1.56%). The results of the Chi Square test with a p value of 0.000 (< 0.05) then H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted, which means that there is a relationship between the mother's knowledge and the visit of the toddler to the posyandu in Kotarindau Village, Dolo District, Sigi Regency.

It was found that the mother's knowledge was mostly good, this is because most of the mothers already understood about posyandu visits, but there was still a sufficient and insufficient level of knowledge of mothers under five. Continuous education is still needed about the importance of toddler visits to posyandu can be used as an alternative so that mothers' knowledge increases. A person's level of knowledge greatly affects individual behavior, where the higher the level of knowledge of a mother about the benefits of posyandu, the higher the level of awareness to participate in the posyandu program^{10,11}.

Mothers who are active in bringing their children to the posyandu get information related to the nutritional status of toddlers provided by health workers. The inactivity of mothers in weighing activities at the posyandu causes them not to receive health counseling, not to get vitamin A, and toddlers do not get giving and counseling about supplementary food (PMT)^{7,12}.

Visits to the posyandu, one of which is influenced by the perspective of parents who feel that their children no longer need to be taken to the posyandu as they get older, the distance traveled by the posyandu is busy working or does not have time to bring their toddler children to the posyandu, this is due to a lack of knowledge and attitude about the importance of monitoring growth and development in children under five¹³.

Mothers' knowledge about the Posyandu makes them always take their children to the Posyandu so that it is easy to monitor their growth and development, while mothers who lack knowledge also have less number of visits^{6,14}. Mothers who are not present at the posyandu are worried that information or knowledge about health does not reach all goals, so the goal of changing daily attitudes to behave healthily is difficult to achieve. Even though posyandu is a place to provide educational information¹⁵.

4.2 Hubungan Sikap Ibu dengan Kunjungan Balita ke Posyandu

The results of the *Chi-Square* test with a p value of 0.000 (≤ 0.05), H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted, which means that there is a relationship between the mother's attitude and the visit of toddlers to the posyandu in Kotarindau Village, Dolo District, Sigi Regency. Mothers who have a caring attitude tend to do better in posyandu visits than mothers who have an indifferent attitude tends to be lacking in posyandu visits, this is because attitudes can form certain patterns or ways of thinking in society and vice versa, these patterns of thinking affect people's actions and behaviors, both in daily life and in terms of making important decisions in life.

The attitude that must be possessed by mothers of toddlers towards posyandu includes when coming to the posyandu, mothers want their children to be immunized, mothers can monitor their child's growth and development by going to the posyandu, not thinking that if they go to the posyandu they only want to get additional food, lazy to go to the posyandu because their children are only weighed, and seeing mothers who gossip, even though they are busy, still want to take their children to the posyandu. It is not a deterrent if after immunizing their children with fever, always thinking about the good benefits of going to the posyandu, getting support from their husbands and always bringing KMS or KIA books to see their children's growth and development in writing^{14,15}.

This research is in line with the research of Prasticha et al. that the attitude of mothers who are aware of posyandu is important to improve the health degree of toddlers, and can cause positive behavior of mothers towards posyandu. However, the attitude that has been formed in the mother is not easy to change, because the formation of the attitude is complex and closely related to factors from within and outside the individual itself^{11,16}.

4.3 The Relationship between Mother's Education and Toddler Visits to Posyandu

The results of the Chi Square test with a p value of 0.006 (< 0.05), H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted, which means that there is a relationship between the mother's knowledge and the visit of toddlers to the posyandu in Kotarindau Village, Dolo District, Sigi Regency. High school educated mothers believe in the importance of bringing their children to visit the Posyandu in monitoring growth, development, nutritional status, and the importance of health services. The results of this study were obtained by the majority of respondents who are mothers with high school education with mothers working as housewives (IRT), so they have free time to bring their children to Posyandu.

The low level of education of mothers affects the reception of information so knowledge about Posyandu is limited. The low level of maternal education is an obstacle to health development, this is due to the attitude and behavior that promotes health is still low. The higher the level of maternal education, the lower mortality and morbidity. So that the higher the level of education of the mother, the more active the awareness to visit the Posyandu ^{17,18}.

Research states that education also affects maternal visits at posyandu, higher education will make it easier to understand information, if higher education, then in maintaining health is very concerned, including how to take care of babies and toddlers, regulate balanced nutrition. On the other hand, with low education, it is very difficult to translate the information obtained, both from health workers and from other media ¹⁹.

5. CONCLUSIONS

There is a meaningful relationship between knowledge, attitudes and education of mothers and visits by toddlers to posyandu in Kotarindu Village, Dolo District, Sigi Regency

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